

THE CHARACTERISTICS AND ROLES OF “LIBRARY AS PLACE” IN JAPAN

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Abstract

Libraries as “Places of Public”, where one can experience architectural expression and the legacy of the academic community, are not a new concept in Japan. Public libraries in Japan, have a long history and over the years they have uniquely evolved from “student study room style” (1950s) to “lending library style” (1960s and 1970s) to “network and multimedia style” (1980s to early 1990s), and then to “spatial and user-centered style” (late 1990s to 2000s). This paper would like to examine the characteristics and roles of ‘library as place’ in Japan. We would also like to use these factors to classify Japanese public libraries. By classifying them into types of libraries, we can elucidate the trends and features of the characteristics and roles of the places of public libraries in Japan. Our study used mixed methods of qualitative content analysis and cluster analysis.

We targeted 487 Japanese public libraries that had been inaugurated or renovated since 2010. Among these we were able to collect documents from 128 libraries. Documents collected for the analysis included (1) strategic plans, (2) service plans, and (3) construction plans. Descriptions of the place and spaces were assigned codes using the qualitative analysis software MAXQDA. We then developed a typology of public libraries based on cluster analysis. We examined each cluster and classified them.

As a result of the qualitative content analysis, 5,581 codes were derived and divided into 13 code groups. Most libraries had two major code groups, “contribution to community building” and “meeting user needs through space development”. In other words, both code groups typically represent the characteristics and roles of Japanese public libraries today. In addition, cluster analysis was conducted on the code groups, and the libraries were classified into six library types: (1) modern basic, (2) progressive, (3) community-development, (4) information-centered, (5) civic and social-centered, and (6) traditional service-oriented.

Future research of each type could further clarify the actual role of library spaces for citizens and local communities.

Keywords: Library as Place, public libraries, qualitative content analysis, cluster analysis, Japan.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Contemporary public library space

In recent years, technological developments have made it possible to access knowledge materials without visiting a library. At the same time, specifically in the 1990s, the concept of “Library as place” emerged as a counterargument to the theory of the library disappearance (Birdsall, 1994; Buschman & Leckie, 2007; Hapel, 2012; Kuno, 2014; Wiegand, 2005). The theory of “Library as place” argues that libraries are not mere collections of electronic information resources that e-books and digital libraries can easily replace but have various social and cultural roles based on their location, and that their existence is meaningful (Kuno, 2014). For example, Helsinki Central Library Oodi is a meeting place, a house of reading and a place to experience diverse urban activities (Koizumi & Larsen, 2022). In addition to places dedicated to reading, there is also a music studio, a movie theater, and a 3D printer that can be used freely. This library allows people to experience creative encounters with materials and information.

Similar libraries also exist in Japan. For instance, Sirius in the Yamato City is a complex facility that integrates library, art and culture hall, children's plaza, and other facilities within the same building (Yamato mirai, n.d.). Similarly, Musashino Place, Musashino City, is a facility that functions as a library, and as centers for lifelong learning support, youth activity support, and civic activity support (Musashino Place, n.d.).

1.2 Changing space of Japanese public libraries

Public libraries in Japan have been used in various ways over time. In the 1950s libraries had the “student study room style,” characterized by the fact that most users were students, who on average stayed longer and sought a quiet environment (Uematsu, 2014). Later, in the 1960s and 1970s, documents published by the Japan Library Association led to the enhancement of lending services, resulting in the “lending library style “with housewives and children as their main users. Between the 1980s to the early 1990s, the high economic growth combined with the users’ needs led to the diversification of library services. Diversified services, driven by a growing awareness of lifelong learning, led to the current form of “spatial and user-centered style “libraries (Uematsu, 2014). These libraries, according to the “Mission and Goals of Public Libraries,” published by the Japan Library Association (2004) are spaces for “meeting, talking, and interacting with people and participating in the creation of local culture.” Space and place have become important elements of public libraries in Japan.

However, at present, the definition of the concept of spatial and user-centered style library is ambiguous. There is also a need to further examine the reality of the role of place and space of Japanese public libraries in the 21st century.

1.3 Research objectives

“Place” is an important element for Japanese public libraries in the 21st century, but its current status of characteristics and roles from the perspectives of culture, knowledge or social transference is still unclear. Since place-centered library development, which is emphasized worldwide, can also be seen in Japan, we believe that research on place in Japanese public libraries will contribute to the future development of public libraries in Japan. The purpose of this study is to comprehensively identify and typify the characteristics and role of place in contemporary Japanese public libraries. The study also aims to develop a foundation for future discussions regarding places in Japanese public libraries.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

In a prior study, Kawamoto & Koizumi (2019), captured the “library as place” discussion, and identified “wisdom,” “heritage,” and “community” as its three symbolic foundations. Under “wisdom,” there are two dimensions of “intelligence” and “creativity”; under “heritage,” there are three dimensions of “culture and history,” “empowerment,” and “neutrality”; and under “community,” three dimensions of publicness,” “sociability,” and “friendliness” are said to exist. There are an additional 25 sub-dimensions under these eight dimensions, indicating that the library as a place is being discussed from many different aspects. However, this study did not survey the Japanese literature.

Regarding research on “library as place” in Japan, Kuno (2016) mentioned that “library as place” research has started as a new library research mainly in the United States, and, “the recognition of this

has not yet spread very widely.” To date, there have been no large-scale surveys on the characteristics and role of public library places in Japan, and there is no systematic analysis of the reality of “library as place” in Japan.

3 METHOD

In this study, a qualitative content analysis was conducted to systematically clarify the characteristics and role of places in the contemporary Japanese public library. Specifically, the elements of the characteristic and roles of library as place were extracted by assigning codes to the content of planning documents of various Japanese public libraries. The target samples were libraries that had been newly opened or renovated after 2010. Initially, 487 public libraries were considered. Written documents on concepts and plans, which were formulated at the time the target libraries were opened or renovated, such as project concepts, business plans, service plans, construction plans, were collected. Documents that contained only architectural drawings or were mainly questions and answers in the Congress were excluded from the analysis.

If a search using the Internet did not turn up applicable documents, inquiries were made to the libraries and municipalities by e-mail, fax, or telephone. When inquiries revealed the existence of documents, we requested that the data be sent by e-mail or mailed, and target documents were collected for analysis. Of the 487 libraries targeted for data collection, we collected documents from 139 libraries, 160 libraries did not respond. Additional, 188 libraries responded that no records existed or provided materials that were determined irrelevant by the authors. In some cases, more than one document was collected per library, the total number of documents used for analysis was 147. In Fig.1 below, the year the libraries were opened (n=139) is shown.

Figure 1. Number of libraries by year of opening/renovated.

Codes were assigned to the collected documents using the MAXQDA2020 qualitative analysis software. Open coding was utilized, and the definitions were written in the coding manual each time a new code was created.

After extracting the characteristics and roles of library places, types of public libraries were created through cluster analysis of the extracted characteristics. The k-means method, a typical non-hierarchical clustering methodology was applied. The process of qualitative content analysis and clustering is shown in Fig.2.

Figure 2. Research Procedure.

4 RESULT

4.1 Results of qualitative content analysis

"Descriptions of the characteristics and roles of the modern Japanese public library places were extracted from the analyzed materials, and a total of 5,581 codes were assigned. These codes were classified into the following 13 code groups: *"promoting the use of facilities and services," "contribution to community building," "contribution to regional development," "provision of and encouragement to utilize information," "education and learning," "support for research," "support for better reading," "meeting user needs through space development," "contribution to development of local industry," "inspiration for users," "support for disadvantaged people," "support for civic activities," and "foundations of democracy"*. In some code groups, depending on the content, subcode groups were used for organizing the content clearly.

The *"promoting the use of facilities and services"* was a group of codes for intentions to increase the number of users of library facilities and services, in accordance with the library development directive and included codes such as "promotion of usage by multiple usage". The "promotion of usage by multiple usage" was assigned to descriptions that intend to attract citizens by establishing the library as a complex facility, for citizens who are not interested in just visiting a library.

The *"contribution to community building"* was a group of codes for intentions to promote the building and development of the local community through library activities. This code group consists of two sub-code groups: "making connections between users" and "bringing people together".

The *"contribution to regional development"* was a group of codes for intentions to contribute to the development of the region, which was broader than local community mentioned above. "encouraging/fostering civic pride" was a typical code of this code group. This code was given to descriptions that highlighted the citizens' attachment to and pride in their community through the existence of the library and its use.

The *"provision of and encouragement to utilize information"* was a group of code to make the library an institution where information will/should be gathered, provided, and its use promoted, in accordance with users' demands. This code group consisted of three sub-code groups: "collection, preservation, and use of local materials," "provision of various information to users," and "support for information use."

The *"education and learning"* was a group of code that intends for the library to be a place for learning and a center for education. This group of codes included codes for intentions to make the library a place for learning based on the use of materials and information, to provide study rooms in the library, to create learning opportunities through events and exhibitions, and to provide and support lifelong learning opportunities.

The “*support for research*” was a group of codes that includes codes related to support for citizens' research activities that are conducted with a clearer sense of purpose and problem rather than education and learning. Specifically, the code was given to descriptions that aimed at providing space for research activities and facilities where researchers visiting from inside and outside the region could receive support for their research activities.

The “*support for better reading*” was a code group that included codes that stated that the library intended to become a facility for the promotion of reading activities and a place that provides a reading environment for users.

The “*meeting user needs through space development*” was a code group for intentions to meet users' needs through zoning of the building and development of spaces with various characteristics and purposes.

The “*contribution to development of local industry*” was a set of codes that were intended to link the library activities to the industrial development of the region. Specifically, it included codes such as “contribute to tourism,” which was intended to make the library a facility that contributes to attracting tourists to the area.

The “*inspiration for users*” code group was intended to contribute to the mental development of users through library spaces and activities. This code group consisted of three sub-code groups: “place for creation,” “support for cultural activities,” and “contribution to users' spiritual development.

The “*support for disadvantaged people*” was a set of codes intended for libraries to be institutions that provide support for the socially disadvantaged and minorities, such as the disabled, the elderly, and foreigners.

The “*support for civic activities*” was a code group that promoted the revitalization of local civic activities by making the library a facility that provides places and opportunities for civic activities and circle activities. This code group includes codes such as “place for presentation of results” to revitalize civic activities by providing a place to present and exhibit the results of civic activities, and “civic collaboration” to describe the library as a facility that was built together with citizens and provides a place for civic collaboration.

The “*foundations of democracy*” code group was intended for libraries to guarantee citizens' right to know through the provision of information. Codes were given to descriptions that link the provision of information by libraries to democracy, and to descriptions that intend to be a place that brings users and local governments together through events and activities at libraries.

The code group with the highest number of codes given to materials was “contribution to regional development” with 1,123 codes, followed by “meeting user needs through space development” with 916 codes and “provision of and encouragement to utilize information” with 748 codes. In contrast, the code group with the lowest number of assignments was “foundations of democracy” with only 18 assignments.

The results of this survey showed that the Japanese public libraries were strongly aware of their roles, which were for citizens “to meet, talk, and interact with people and participate in the creation of local culture,” “to obtain information and knowledge necessary for daily life and work,” and “to come into contact with materials and obtain information useful for solving problems in administration, education, culture, and industry in the community where they live,” (items listed by the Japan Library Association). On the other hand, the role of the library as a place to “come into contact with various ideas and views on political and social issues and use them as food for deciding one's own ideas” was not often used for describing the library place.

4.2 Results of cluster analysis

In the k-means method, each of the 13 code groups obtained was treated as a dimension, and each public library to be analyzed was used as data with features expressed as a 13-dimensional vector. Cluster analysis was then performed on the data to obtain a type of public libraries. Data with extremely small numbers of codes (less than 10) were excluded from the analysis, resulting in 136 data items and 128 libraries. As a result, the libraries were classified into six types. They were then named.

The “**Modern basic library**” was a type of library that was assigned many codes included in the two code groups of “contribution to community building” and “meeting user needs through space development”. “Contribution to community building” and “meeting user needs through space development” were given codes in many cases and were often cited as features in other typologies,

making them major characteristics in the function and nature of the place of public libraries in Japan today. Characteristics of the “modern basic type” were often described in the basic policy section of the overall library, and similar descriptions can be found in the detailed plans. It was evident that the library was viewed as a place for citizen interaction and community activities, and that the libraries were aware of the need to develop space for this purpose.

The “**Progressive library**” was a type of library that was assigned many codes included in the four code groups of “contribution to community building”, “meeting user needs through space development”, “inspiration for users”, “provision of and encouragement to utilize information”. This was the only type in which there were four code groups that can be identified as characteristics, the largest number among the types identified in this study. This type of library only included libraries that were opened after 2015. This indicated that, especially in recent years, libraries from the planning process were being built with a strong awareness of the characteristics and role of place. Libraries belonging to the “Progressive type” also played a role in promoting cultural and creative activities, as well as the accumulation and use of information. To realize these roles, libraries were designed to have a variety of interior spaces with different characteristics, and to provide a place for interaction.

The “**Community-development library**” was a type of library characterized by three code groups: “contribution to community building,” “contribution to regional development,” and “support for civic activities”. In particular, “contribution to community building” and “contribution to regional development” could be identified as strong characteristics of these libraries. In addition, “contribution to regional development” was a code group that was recognized as a feature only in this type. Libraries belonging to this category intended to be places for community building and development, to create liveliness in the community, and to contribute to local vitalization. To achieve these goals, these libraries were positioned as places that promote civic activities and collaboration with citizens.

The “**Information-centered library**” was characterized by three groups of codes: “contribution to community building”, “provision of and encouragement to utilize information” and “meeting user needs through space development” Especially, “provision of and encouragement to utilize information” showed up as a strong feature compared to the other two code groups. Libraries belonging to the “advanced information provider type” viewed the library as a place where information is gathered and a place that connects citizens/users with information, and to improve the library's interior space to enhance its effectiveness. This type included four of the five prefectural libraries analyzed in this study. This suggests that prefectural libraries considered the characteristic of the library place where information and citizens/people gathered, to be significant. This may be because prefectural libraries are responsible for advanced information services that municipal/city libraries cannot handle due to the collection size and human resources. This role of prefectural libraries has been specialized more in helping users' research and directing local libraries by functional differentiation accompanied by the more complex library network developed in the 1980s.

The “**Civic and social-centered library**” was characterized by three groups of codes: “contribution to community building”, “meeting user needs through space development” and “support for civic activities”. In particular, “meeting user needs through space development” was the strongest feature of the type. Libraries belonging to the “place for civic activities type” had spaces with diverse characteristics within the building, with the nature of each space within the building defined in detail from its planning process. Many spaces with functions to support civic and circle activities have been established, suggesting that the public library played a role as a place for civic activities, and was intended to be a facility where people and activities could gather and contribute to the development of the community.

The “**Traditional service-oriented library**” was a type that did not have a set of codes that characterized its function as a place. The reason for the absence of a distinctive code group was because of the small number of codes assigned to the materials. The background for the small number of codes assigned was due to the limited description provided in the collected materials and the fact that the library space was not assigned with any special function or characteristics. However, it cannot be considered that these libraries did not have the characteristic and the role of a library place. Rather the lack of descriptions in the planning phase documents suggest that the places belonging to this library type may have traditional characteristics and roles seen in most Japanese libraries.

5 CONCLUSION

This study, conducted a qualitative content analysis with the goal of comprehensively identifying the traits and role of the library place in contemporary Japan, resulting in the derivation of a set of 13 code

groups. Among them, the two code groups “contribution to community building” and “meeting user needs through space development” had the highest number of codes assigned and were mentioned as characteristics in many clusters. From this, it can be said that these code groups were representative of the characteristic and the role of public library places in contemporary Japan. One of the reasons for this could be the influence of community policies that began in Japan after 1970. Communities that were built as a response to the weakening regional ties, were considered as a necessity, even after the 2000 due to repeated disasters. In addition, as public facilities become more complex and the functions of library places increase, libraries, have become places for people to gather. This has increased the use of library spaces for civic and social engagements.

Furthermore, a cluster analysis was used to create a category for public libraries in contemporary Japan. Cluster analysis was also used to develop types of public libraries in contemporary Japan. Six types were obtained, modern basic library, which strongly expresses two typical characteristics of the modern Japanese public library place, as well as the progressive library, the community-development library, the information-centered library, the civic and social-centered library, and the traditional service-oriented library.

Studies like ours are not without their limitations. The documents analyzed in this study were mostly concepts and plans that were developed before the public libraries became functional. Hence, the characteristics and roles identified in this study revealed only the intentions of the library establishment. Our future research agenda, therefore, would be to clarify whether the intentions in the documents have been transformed to practice in modern Japanese public libraries.

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